

An Application of Galerkins Method to Diffusion of Oxygen in The Living Tissue

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Reeta Dixit

Assistant Professor
Department Of
Mathematics
D. A. V. P.G. College
Kanpur ,Uttar Pradesh
India

Abstract

Gherkin's method has been applied to solve the coupled partial differential equations for the capillary and tissue regions, for the diffusion of oxygen in the living tissue in the steady state, for both constant and linear metabolic rates in the tissue region. The results obtained have been compared with those obtained earlier by Krogh (1919 a, b, c), Blum (1960), Reneau et al (1966) and others. The method has been extended to cover the following cases:

1. consideration of actual velocity profile in the capillary region
2. consideration of axial diffusion in the capillary region
3. possibility of entry oxygen concentration depending on the radial distance from the axis
4. consideration of non-linear Michaelis–Melton kinetics.

Keywords

Partial Pressure p_a The concentration c_a , Radius r_c , Radius of the outer r_t , Permeability P , Diffusivities D_{Hb} , D_b and D_t .

Introduction

The supply of oxygen to the living tissue cells of skeletal muscle, lungs or brain for their inspiration is a vital function of the human body. The oxygen is supplied through the process of dissociation of oxygen from the oxy-hemoglobin of the red cells into the blood plasma, its diffusion in the blood plasma, its transport across the capillary walls, and finally its diffusion through the tissue cells.

Objective of study

The basic model is that of Krogh cylinder structure where it is postulated that: (i) each cylindrical capillary supplies oxygen exclusively to one coaxial cylindrical tissue region. (ii) the capillaries are of equal radii. (iii) the tissue regions have the same thickness. (iv) the capillaries and tissues are uniformly dispersed in the system concerned (Fig. 1 and 2).

One wants to investigate as to how the supply of oxygen to a tissue cell depends on:

1. Its location in the tissue
2. Velocity of blood flow in the capillary
3. The partial pressure p_a of oxygen at the arterial end
4. The concentration c_a of oxygen at the entry
5. The radius r_c of the capillary wall
6. The radius r_t of the outer or no-flux surface of the tissue cylinder
7. The permeability P of the capillary wall, Diffusivities D_{Hb} , D_b and D_t of oxygen in hemoglobin, plasma, and tissue respectively.

In particular one wants to understand what happens when one inhales oxygen at low pressures such as at high altitudes or when a patient inhales pure oxygen at a high pressure. One also wants to know as to which portions of the tissue, if any, are likely to suffer from lack of oxygen.

Review of Literature

Extensive work on oxygen diffusion in living tissues has been done by Krogh (1919, a,b,c), Hill (1928), Opitz and Schneider (1950), Thews (1960), Blum (1960), Bloach (1962), Reneau et al (1966), and Middleman (1972). In each case, the partial differential equations for the concentration $c(r,z,t)$ oxygen, one for the capillary region and the other

for the tissue region (Fig. 2) are written and these are solved subject to boundary conditions on the axis of the capillary, on the capillary wall and the no-flux surface of the tissue cylinder.

Different solutions differ in the assumptions made and the approximation used. These concern

1. isotropy of diffusion of oxygen in blood
2. neglect of dissociation of oxygen in hemoglobin
3. rate of consumption of oxygen in tissue
4. neglect of axial diffusion
5. steady or non-steady state
6. averaging of velocity in the capillary
7. considering only average of concentration in each section of the capillary
8. equation of curve between oxygen saturation fraction and partial pressure of oxygen
9. approximation involved in numerical integration.

Main Text

Methodology

The methods used are based on separation of variables, determination of eigenvalues, or on straightforward numerical integration. We use Galerkin's method to solve the partial differential equations for the tissue and capillary regions, which are coupled by the boundary conditions at the interface. We obtain solutions for both constant and linear metabolic rates of consumption of oxygen in the tissue and examine the difficulty involved in extending the method to non-linear rates. This method may give a better approximation than the classical approximations obtained earlier and can give a better analytical insight that can be obtained by numerical methods.

Analysis

Basic Equation

We shall assume steady state, no axial diffusion, no dissociation of oxygen, isotropy of diffusion in blood and, for the present, an average blood velocity in the capillary. Let $c(r, z, t)$ be the concentration of oxygen, D_1, D_2 be the diffusivities of oxygen in the capillary and tissue regions, r_c, r_t the radii of capillary and the no-flux surfaces of the tissue cylinder, P the permeability of the capillary wall, u the average velocity of blood in the capillary and g_0 be the constant rate of metabolism per unit volume in the tissue region. Also let suffixes b, t, a and v refer to blood region, tissue region, arterial end and venous respectively, then we have the following basic equations:

(i) Capillary region

$$u \frac{\partial c}{\partial z} = D_1 \left(\frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial c}{\partial r} \right)$$

(ii) Tissue region

$$0 = D_2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial c}{\partial r} \right) - g_0$$

(iii) Boundary Conditions

$$\left[\frac{\partial c}{\partial r} \right]_b = 0 \quad \text{at } r=0$$

$$- \left[D_1 \frac{\partial c}{\partial r} \right]_b = - D_2 \left[\frac{\partial c}{\partial r} \right]_t = P[(c)_b - (c)_t] \quad \text{at } r = r_c$$

(4)

$$\left[\frac{\partial c}{\partial r} \right]_t = 0 \quad \text{at } r = r_t$$

(5)

$$[c]_b = c_z \quad \text{at } z=0$$

(6)

Solution of The Equation For The Tissue Region

Equation (2) can be written as

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left[r \frac{\partial c}{\partial r} \right] = \frac{g_0}{D_2} r \tag{7}$$

Integrating and using (5)

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial r} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{g_0}{D_2} \left(r - \frac{r_t^2}{r} \right)$$

(8)

Integrating again

$$c(r, z) = \frac{g_0}{D_2}$$

(9)

$$c(r, z) = \frac{g_0}{D_2} \left[\frac{r^2}{4} - \frac{r_t^2}{2} \ln r \right] + B(z)$$

Define

(10)

Then

$$c_0(z) = c(r_c, z)$$

$$c_0(z) = \frac{g_0}{D_2} \left[\frac{r_c^2}{4} - \frac{r_t^2}{2} \right] \tag{11}$$

So that

$$c(r, z) - c_0(z) = \frac{g_0}{D_2} \left[\frac{r^2 - r_c^2}{4} - \frac{r_t^2}{2} \ln \frac{r}{r_c} \right]$$

(12)

Thus $c(r, z)$ is the sum of a function of z and a function of r . This function of z , which represents the concentration of oxygen on the inter-face on the blood side, will be

determined in the next section through the solution of the partial differential equation for the capillary region and the use of the boundary conditions at the interface.

Solution For The Capillary Region

(a) Partial Differential Equation and Boundary Conditions for the Laplace Transform of the Oxygen Concentration

We have to solve (1) subject to (3), (4), and (6). Let $\bar{c}(r, s)$ be the Laplace transform of $c(r, z)$ so that:

$$\bar{c}(r, s) = \int_0^\infty e^{-sz} c(r, z) dz,$$

Then equations (1), (3), (4), and (6) give on making use of (13)

$$\frac{D_1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial \bar{c}}{\partial r} \right) = u(\bar{c}s - c_a)$$

$$\frac{\partial \bar{c}}{\partial r} = 0 \quad \text{at } r=0 \tag{15}$$

$$-D_1 \left[\frac{\partial \bar{c}}{\partial r} \right]_{r=r_c} = -g_0 \left[\frac{r_c}{2} - \frac{r_t^2}{2 r_t^2} \frac{1}{s} \right]$$

$$= P[\bar{c}(r_c, s)]_b - [\bar{c}(r_c, s)]_t$$

$$-D_1 \left[\frac{\partial \bar{c}}{\partial r} \right]_{r=r_c} = \frac{A}{s} = P[\bar{c}_1(s) - \bar{c}_0(s)]$$

$$A = \frac{1}{2} g_0 \left[\frac{r_t^2}{r_c} - r_c \right]$$

Where $\bar{c}_1(s)$ and $\bar{c}_0(s)$ are the Laplace transforms of the oxygen concentration on the interface of the blood and tissue sides respectively.

b) Galerkin's Functions

According to Galerkin's method, we first try to get a set of functions satisfying the boundary conditions (15) and (17). We try

$$\bar{c}(r, s) - \bar{c}_0 \tag{19}$$

Equation (15) is satisfied identically, Equation (17) gives

$$-D_2 \frac{b_1}{s} 2i r_c^{2i-1} = \frac{A}{s} = P \left[\frac{a_1}{s} + \frac{b_1}{s} + r_c^{2i} \right]$$

(20)

So that

$$s_1 = \frac{A}{P} + \frac{A}{D_1} \frac{1}{2i} r_c, \quad b_1 = - \frac{A}{D_1} \frac{1}{2i r_c^{2i-1}}$$

$$h_1(r_c) = a_1 + b_1 r_c^{2i} = - \frac{D_1}{P} b_1 2i r_c^{2i-1} = \frac{A}{P}$$

(21)

(22)

We now generalise (19) to try the more general solution

$$\bar{c}(r, s) - \bar{c}_0(s) = \frac{1}{s} \sum_{i=1}^n f_1(s) (a_1 + b_1 r^{2i})$$

$$= \sum_{i=1}^n (a_1 + b_1 r^{2i}) f_1(s) \tag{23}$$

where a_1 and b_1 are given by (21), and the functions $f_1(s)$ will be determined from the condition that (23) should satisfy (14) as closely as possible.

This satisfies (15) and it also satisfies (17) if

$$\sum_{i=1}^n f_1(s) = 1$$

(24)

Substituting from (23) in (14), the residual is

$$R(r, s) = \frac{D_1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial \bar{c}}{\partial r} \right) - u[\bar{c}s - c_r]$$

$$= \frac{D_1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n f_1(s) h_1(r) \right] = u s \bar{c}_0(s) + \sum_{i=1}^n f_1(s) h_1(r) - c_0 s$$

So that

$$\sum_{i=1}^n s R(r, s) = D_1 \sum_{i=1}^n f_1(s) \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial h_1}{\partial r} \right) - u \{ s \bar{c}_0(s) - c_0 s \} - u s \sum_{i=1}^n f_1(s) h_1(r)$$

(c) Determination of $f_1(s)$ and $c_0(s)$

We now choose $f_1(s)$ and $c_0(s)$ so as to make the residual orthogonal to $h_1(r), h_2(r), \dots, h_n(r)$ over the interval $(0, r_c)$. This gives

$$\int_0^{r_c} R(r, s) h_j(r) dr = 0 \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

(26)

Or $\sum_{i=1}^n a_{ij} f_1(s) + s \sum_{i=1}^n b_{ij} f_1(s) = p_j [s^2 c_0(s) - c_a s]$

(27)

where on making use of (19), (21) and (22) and putting

$$Sh_w = \frac{Pr_c}{D_1}$$

$$a_{ij} = -D_1 \int_0^{r_c} \frac{1}{r} \left(r \frac{\partial h_1}{\partial r} \right) h_j(r) dr$$

We get

$$= \frac{A^2 r_c^2}{D_1} \frac{Sh_w + 2i + 2j}{2i + 2j} \frac{Sh_w}{Sh_w}$$

$$b_{ij} = u \int_0^{r_c} h_1(r) h_j(r) r dr$$

$$= \frac{1}{8} u \frac{A^2}{P^2} r_c^2 \left[\frac{Sh_w 2(i+j+2)}{(i+1)(j+1)(i+j+1)} + \frac{2Sh_w(i+j+2)}{(i+1)(j+1)} + 4 \right]$$

$$P_j = -u \int_0^{r_c} h_j(r) r dr$$

$$= -\frac{1}{2} u \frac{A}{P} r_c^2 \left[1 + \frac{Sh_w}{2(j+1)} \right]$$

Equations (24) and (27) give (n+1) equations to determine the(n+1) transforms $f_1(s), f_2(s), \dots, f_n(s)$ and $c_0(s)$. Substituting.

$$s^2 \bar{c}_0(s) - c_s s = \phi(s), \quad f_i(s) = \phi(s) \psi_i(s) \tag{32}$$

We get the equations

$$\sum_{i=1}^n (a_{ij} + s b_{ij}) \psi_i(s) = p_j, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots \tag{33}$$

And

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \psi_i(s) = [\phi(s)]^{-1} \tag{34}$$

From (33) we get

$$\psi_i(s) = \frac{N_i(s)}{D(s)} \tag{35}$$

where $N_i(s)$ and $D(s)$ are polynomials of (n-1) th and n th degrees respectively, and

$$D(s) = |a_{ij} + s b_{ij}| \tag{36}$$

It is easily seen from (29) and (30) that (a_{ij}) and (b_{ij}) are symmetric matrices with all positive elements. Further, if $D(s)=0$, then the system of equations

$$(a_{i1} + s b_{i1})x_1 + (a_{i2} + s b_{i2})x_2 + \dots + (a_{in} + s b_{in})x_n = 0, \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, n) \tag{37}$$

has a non-zero solution. Multiplying these equations by X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n

$$\sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^n a_{ij} x_i x_j + s \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^n b_{ij} x_i x_j = 0 \tag{38}$$

If $x_j = a_j + \sqrt{-1}B_j$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^n a_{ij} x_i x_j &= \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^n a_{ij} (a_j + \sqrt{-1}B_j)(a_i + \sqrt{-1}B_i) \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^n a_{ij} (a_i a_j - B_i B_j) + \sqrt{-1} \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^n a_{ij} (a_i B_j + a_j B_i) \\ &> \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^n a_{ij} B_i B_j > 0 \end{aligned} \tag{39}$$

Similarly,

$$\sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^n b_{ij} x_i x_j > 0 \tag{40}$$

Equation (38) then shows that all roots of (38) are real and negative. Assuming that all there are distinct, we get the form

$$\psi_i(s) = \frac{A_{i1}}{s + r_1} + \frac{A_{i2}}{s + r_2} + \dots + \frac{A_{in}}{s + r_n}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n \tag{41}$$

where all the r's are positive, so that

$$L^{-1}[\psi_i(s)] = A_{i1}e^{-r_1z} + A_{i2}e^{-r_2z} + \dots + A_{in}e^{-r_nz} \tag{42}$$

where $A_j = \sum_{i=1}^n A_{ji}$
 (44)

$$f_i(s) = \psi(s)\psi_i(s) = \frac{\frac{A_{i1}}{s+r_1} + \frac{A_{i2}}{s+r_2} + \dots + \frac{A_{in}}{s+r_n}}{\frac{A_1}{s+r_1} + \frac{A_2}{s+r_2} + \dots + \frac{A_n}{s+r_n}} = \frac{P_i(s)}{P(s)} \tag{45}$$

So that

$$s^2\bar{c}_o(s) - c_a s = \frac{1}{\frac{A_1}{s+r_1} + \frac{A_2}{s+r_2} + \dots + \frac{A_n}{s+r_n}} = \frac{Q(s)}{P(s)} \tag{46}$$

Where

$$P_i(s) = \sum_{j=1}^n A_{ji}(s+r_1)(s+r_2)\dots(s+r_{j+1})\dots(s+r_n) \tag{47}$$

$$P(s) = \sum_{j=1}^n A_j(s+r_1)(s+r_2)\dots(s+r_{j-1})(s+r_{j+1})\dots(s+r_n) \tag{48}$$

$$Q(s) = (s+r_1)(s+r_2)\dots(s+r_n) \tag{49}$$

So that $P_i(s)$ $P(s)$ are polynomials of (n-1)th degree and Q(s) is a polynomial of nth degree. Let

$$w_i(z) = L^{-1}\left[\frac{f_i(s)}{s}\right] = L^{-1}\left[\frac{P_i(s)}{sP(s)}\right], \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n \tag{50}$$

$$w(z) = L^{-1}\left[\frac{Q(s)}{s^2P(s)}\right] \tag{51}$$

Then from (23), (45), (50), (51), we get

$$c(r, z) - c_0(z) = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i(z) h_i(r) = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i(z) (a_i + b_i r^{2i}) \tag{52}$$

Equation (53) determines $c_0(z)$ the oxygen concentration on the interface

$$c_0(z) = c_a + w(z) \tag{53}$$

Equation (53) determines $c_0(z)$, the oxygen concentration on the interface On the tissue side. Its substitution in (12) then determines the oxygen concentration at any point in the tissue region. From (52) and (53)

$$c(r, z) = c_a + w(z) + \sum_{i=1}^n w_i(z) (a_i + b_i r^{2i}) \tag{54}$$

Equation (54) determines the concentration of oxygen at any point in the capillary region. In particular it gives for the interface on the blood side on making use of equation (22)

$$\begin{aligned} c_1(z) &= c(r_c, z) = c_a + w(z) + \sum_{i=1}^n w_i(z) (a_i + b_i r_c^{2i}) \\ &= c_0(z) = \frac{A}{P} \sum_{i=1}^n w_i(z) = c_0(z) + \frac{A}{P} L^{-1} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{f_1(s)}{s} \right] \\ &= c_0(z) + \frac{A}{P} \end{aligned} \tag{55}$$

which is a consequence of (17)

(d) Solution when n=1

In this case from (23), (24) and (27)

$$\begin{aligned} f_1(s) &= 1, s^2\bar{c}_0(s) - c_a s = \frac{1}{p_1} [a_{11} + b_{11}s] \\ \bar{c}(r, s) - \bar{c}_0(s) &= \frac{1}{s} (a_1 + b_1 r^2) \end{aligned} \tag{56}$$

Where from (21), (29), (30) and (31)

$$a_1 = \frac{A}{P} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{A}{D_1} r_c, b_1 = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{A}{D_1} \frac{1}{r_c}, p_1 = -\frac{uA}{2P} r_c^2 \left[1 + \frac{Sh_w}{4} \right] \tag{57}$$

$$a_{11} = \frac{A^2}{4D_1} r_c^2 \left[1 + \frac{Sh_w}{4} \right] +, b_{11} = \frac{4A^2}{8P^2} \left[\frac{Sh_w^2}{3} + 2Sh_w + 4 \right] \tag{58}$$

$$\bar{c}_0(s) = \frac{c_a}{s} + \frac{a_{11}}{p_1 s^2} + \frac{b_{11}}{p_1} \frac{1}{s_1} \tag{59}$$

$$[c(r, z)]_b = c_0(z) + (a_1 + b_1 r^2) = c_a + \frac{b_{11}}{p_1} + a_1 + b_1 r^2 + \frac{a_{11}}{p_1} z \tag{60}$$

$$[c(r, z)]_t = c_0(z) + \frac{g_0}{D_2} \left[\frac{r^2 - r_c^2}{4} - \frac{r_c^2}{2} \ln \frac{r}{r_c} \right] \tag{61}$$

and the minimum concentration of oxygen occurs at the no flux surface at the venous end. If l is the length of the capillary, this is given by

$$c_{min} = c_a + \frac{b_{11}}{p_1} + \frac{a_{11}}{p_1}I + \frac{g_0}{D_2} \left[\frac{r_t^2 - r_c^2}{4} - \frac{r_t^2}{1} In \frac{r}{r_c} \right] \tag{62}$$

Here we have used the fact that since $a_{11} > 0, p_1 < 0, c_0(z), [c(r, z)]_{t}$ all decreases linearly with z. The coefficient of z is given by

$$\frac{a_{11}}{p_1} = -\frac{2AP}{D_1} \frac{1}{u} \frac{1}{Sh_w} = -\frac{2a}{u} \frac{1}{r_c} = -\frac{g_0}{u} \left(\frac{r_t^2}{r_c^2} - 1 \right) \tag{63}$$

This is the same as for the solution obtained by Blum(1960).

(e) solution when n^2

Conclusion

When $n=2$, we get on proceeding as above solutions of the form

$$c_0(z) = p_{11} + p_{12}z + p_{13}e^{-\lambda_1 z} \tag{64}$$

$$c(r, z) = c_0(z) + (q_{11} + q_{12}e^{-\lambda_1 z})(a_1 + b_1 r^2) + (1 - q_{11} + q_{12}e^{-\lambda_1 z})(a_2 + b_2 r^2) \tag{65}$$

For general values of n, we expect solutions of the form

$$c_0(z) = p_{n1} + p_{n2}z + p_{n3}e^{-\lambda_1 z} + \dots p_{nn2}e^{-\lambda_1 z} \tag{66}$$

$$c(r, z) = c_0(z) + \sum_{i=1}^n (q_{i1} + q_{i2}e^{-\lambda_1 z} + \dots q_{in-1}e^{-\lambda_1 z})(a_i + b_i r^2) \tag{67}$$

Where

$$\sum_{i=1}^n q_{i1} = \sum_{i=1}^n q_{i2} = \sum_{i=1}^n q_{in-1} = 1 \tag{68}$$

Of course, we have to calculate the solution for each n for given numerical values of the parameters

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